

Original Article

Exploring how ChatGPT Impact Teaching Practices and Professional Growth: A Case Study of Higher Education Institutions of Sukkur District

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Abstract

The present study aimed to explore the impact of ChatGPT on teachers' teaching practices as well as professional growth of teachers at higher education institutes of Sukkur District. The qualitative design of research was adopted in this explorative study. For gathering the data, the semi-structured interviews were conducted from the faculty members of higher education institutions of Sukkur district. While, the data was analyzed by using thematic analysis. However, the findings disclosed that ChatGPT is powerful tool for educators to improve their teaching practices. Further, it was found that it supports in planning the instruction of lessons, and influences their workflow. Although it is very useful but not a problem free in terms of implementation because it declines the skills of students, has barriers and boundaries of using ChatGPT, and also requires continuous professional growth for the educators. Nonetheless, it is recommended for higher authorities to amend the policies in a way that teachers could have training sessions through which they learn the skills and use the ChatGPT in their teaching practices in an effective way.

Keywords: ChatGPT impact teaching practices and professional growth

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INTRODUCTION

One of the latest trends of technology that has been leaving a positive influence on everyday life of humans is Artificial intelligence (AI). It affects the way things work in normal routine like people before AI have to strive more for searching the information but it has now enabled them to use different search engines, mobile applications, and so on (Sanchez-Prieto et al., 2020). The changing nature of technology has left various effects on teaching strategies of teachers as well as the learning styles of students (Zawacki-Richter et al., 2019). Undoubtedly, the instruction based on AI creates effectiveness in the teaching practices of teachers. In order to take advantage from the sudden transformation in AI technologies the education systems across the globe have started considering its implications while developing the curriculum (Cope et al., 2020).

Indeed, technology has achieved a greater importance indifferent field, i.e. business, commerce, and particularly in Education. Studies have shown that there are evidences of utilization of technology in education i.e. teaching-learning process, still a lot more is needed for making teaching and learning more effective process (Muslem& Juliana, 2017). while, AI is like a milestone in the field of education, because it boosts up the learning of students and the pedagogical skills of teachers (Mulkeen, 1998). It provides the learners the ease of use to knowledge (Alev et al., 2009). The day to day revolution in technology is becoming very easy but a hard process because upgraded technologies demand the new skills known as 21st century skills (Butt et al., 2020). in addition, Wood et al. (2005) has mentioned about integration of AI that in daily learning classrooms it is not a problem free, due to its hindering challenges. Most of professional development programs do not provide opportunities for teachers to utilize technology during class in same manner as they use other tools like black board, chalk, marker etc. (Raby et al., 2010).

In addition, artificial intelligence is one of the most influencing technological tools to upgrade instructing and learning measures. It is also used for understanding the rich context (Ghavifekr et al., 2016). The different studies

show that there are various challenges for implementing it (Mathevula & Uwizeyimana, 2014). The study mentions that in some schools there are facilities of technology, but teachers are using technology only for their personal use. Moreover, they have not expertise in using technology and they have fear to use the technology (Cox, 2008). Despite this Raby & Meunier, (2011) showed in their study that there are challenges which hinder educators to implement AI in their teaching, while students also face the some problems in their learning. Ihmeideh & Al-Maadadi (2018) used teachers' perception to conclude this study. It is also observed that the challenges i.e. human resources, lack of material resources, training and professional development, administrative and parental support.

Moreover, a nationwide survey of teachers and superintendents commissioned by Earle (2002) has observed that technology has an enormous impact in the classroom as students enhance their motivation and information not only in academic terms but also outside the classroom. Still the very little population of teachers use technological gadgets and tools like ChatGPT in classrooms for instructional purposes rather than marketing like graphic designing, spreadsheets, word processing and this is only for personal earning. Also, a variety of other surveys Schoepp (2005) while reporting strong computer usage by teachers, actually indicated a lack of integrated use with the curriculum. In many instances, it has been a case of fitting the curriculum to the computer rather than the computer to the curriculum. Morehead & LaBeau (2005) shared some facts about school technology and these facts unveil the conditions of computers in public education, "The evidences that educators can expect from this and unprecedented support for school technology are not yet clear. There is no guarantee that technology improves student achievement" (Qaddumi et al., 2021).

Whereas, placing computers and software in classrooms is not enough. Discovering whether technology works or not is not the point, but the real issue is when and under what circumstances. Like any other tool, teachers have to come up with a strategy or pedagogy to make it work (Khanghah & Halili, 2015). Indeed, wise use of technology takes adequate training, time, planning, support, and teacher ownership. However, the study concludes that if teachers or school management really wants to integrate artificial intelligence in their classrooms and want positive outcomes then the six factors must be in their place and these factors are leadership, solid educational objectives, professional development, adequate technology resources, time and evaluation, adequate teacher preparation, effective curriculum, supportive school or district administration and supportive family. In other words, establish appropriate conditions by converting restraining forces to facilitating factors.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Barriers that Hinder Educators in Integration of Artificial Intelligence

The findings of the study of Muslem and Juliana (2017) paper finds that both Educators and students see that e-learning: assists students with taking the responsibility for own Learning, gives broadening of exercises, encourages natural force of learning, empowers contemplative person students to interface better, licenses obtaining significant investigation and time the board abilities, permits Educators to have more students' focused type of learning, and so forth. Apart from this, the review of previous studies show some of the main challenges that educators face while implementing the ICT in their teaching and learning process (Ekberg & Gao, 2018). Further challenges i.e. technical challenges, pedagogical challenges, and administrative challenges.

Technical Challenges

These are various hindrances like lack of technical skills, speed of internet and connection problems (Halili & Suguneswary, 2016). While the previous studies shows that lack of technical skills of both teachers as well as students jointly make up this challenge (Amuko et al., 2015). On the other hand, internet speed is another challenge that educators face while using the ICT in education i.e. teaching and learning process (Sivakumar, n.d.). Studies have also concluded that network connection problem also hinder the educators as it is very difficult to be connected to a network for a long time, so it also hinder them (Ghavifekr et al., 2016).

Administrative and Pedagogical challenges

Administering an activity or an appraisal which requires innovative foundation and it is another critical test recognized by the subjects. "Absence of e-learning assets for all classrooms" and "absence of full-time staff to screen the electronic types of gear" are the fundamental difficulties referred to by the members in such manner (Fraij et al., 2009). It is mentioned that there are limited technology resources that's why it is unfair to implement it in curriculum. Furthermore, some teachers have lack of knowledge so that's why they cannot monitor the devices in the class thus it became a big challenge. Meanwhile, some teachers do not feel comfort while using technology in the class, that's why they avoid to use and to teach the students through technology in the class (Unal & Ozturk,

2012). Whereas, the pedagogical skills are very important for teachers while utilizing ICT in classrooms. The self-willingness of teachers' persist them to get mastery on ICT knowledge. Thus, teachers couldn't feel comfort to implement ICT in teaching (Peeraer & Van Petegem, 2010).

Human Resources and Other Relevant Material

The human resources include the people like technician (Reinen & Plomp, 1993). technological tools are of no use once they got out of order, so lack of technical support is rising challenges in schools to overcome the ICT concerned issue (Hinostraza, 2018). Thus it hinders to implement the artificial intelligence in classroom (Fullan, 1992). The study found that there were no technological equipment to be use in the schools, so if there are no material then what to implement. The equipment i.e. computers, multimedia, strong internet connection etc. (Jones, 2004).

Training and Professional Support

Integration of ChatGPT artificial intelligence is becoming hard for teachers because they are not given effective training that how to operate the computers, search engines like ChatGPT or other technical devices (Prasojo et al., 2019). One finding of Schoepp (2005) study was that teachers are not provided with the training opportunities which help teachers to use ChatGPT in classrooms. Moreover, research in Turkey found that the main problem with implementing new technologies in education was the insufficient amount of in-service training for teachers (Ghavifekr & Rosdy, 2015), and Morehead & LaBeau (2005) concluded that limited teachers' training related to the technological trends in Turkish schools is an obstacle. In addition to that, for every work to be done it is necessary that the doer of the work must have an enthusiasm to do that, same case in the process of integration of ICT in classroom. Most of the teachers do not have any interest to use technology in classroom that is why ICT is not being used in classrooms. Meanwhile, in Australian research, Newhouse, Trinidad, & Clarkson (2002) found that many teachers lacked the knowledge and skills to use computers and were unenthusiastic about the changes and integration of supplementary learning associated with bringing computers into their teaching practices.

Mutisya, Mulwa, and Mwanja, (2017) in their study described that the teachers are not given proper training about using technology. If teachers don't know themselves then how they will implement it in classrooms. This is also an interrupting challenge when AI is integrated in classroom (Kong & Li, 2009). Furthermore the support from the school authorities and also the support from other concerned authorities created hindrance in using artificial intelligence in classroom (Puncreobutr, 2016). Additionally, the study of Drury (1995) identified that AI is influential tool for educators to improve teaching practices. However, It is also found in the study that it is an important gadget that not only improve learning of students but also polishes the pedagogical skills of the teachers (Fraj et al., 2010). On the contrary, the school leadership is considered as backbone of school management so school leaders need to utilize the available resource for ICT integration (Lynch, 2006). If technology related tools are not available at schools, the leaders of institutes can sponsor and collaborate other authorities i.e. higher authorities etc, to integrate ICT in classrooms (AbuJarour et al., 2018). However, it is found that in some schools there are material resources but due to the teachers' lack of self-efficacy they are not willing to utilize them (Butt et al., 2020). Self-efficacy is defined as one's confidence or belief in his/her ability to do a task (Fraj et al., 2010). So for improving teachers' self-efficacy school management should arrange the proper training programs (Khanghah & Halili, 2015). More importantly, with rapid increase in technology the school management need to update teachers concerned skills i.e. twenty first century skills (Hennessy et al., 2010).

METHODOLOGY

The qualitative research design is a type of research that enables individuals to have deeper understanding of the subject under investigation. While, present also aimed to explore the barriers that hinder the execution of ChatGPT artificial intelligence in teaching practices of teachers at higher education level in Sukkur District. Qualitative design of research would be the best fit for examining the teaching-practices at university level. More specifically, the case study method could enable the researcher to deeply examine how the teaching practices and professional growth of teacher at HEIs are affected ChatGPT AI. By having a extended focus on the context of study, the adopted research design could offer a detailed understanding of barriers and benefits of utilizing the ChatGPT AI in classroom settings. A purposive sampling is a type of non-probability sampling in adopted for a specific purpose. In this techniques participants chosen based on their special characteristics (Creswell, 2005). It allows the researcher to gather the data from the participants who are most appropriate for case under investigation. The benefit of this technique is that researcher would have the relevant data. The present study included 10 university teacher i.e. lecturers, professors, and teaching assistants from public higher education institutes of

Sukkur District. In Sukkur district there are four higher education institutes i.e. Sukkur IBA University, Arorr University of Arts and Heritage, Ghulam Muhammad Mahar Medical College Sukkur, and Begum Nusrat Bhutto (BNB) Women University Sukkur. The participants were 3 from Sukkur IBA University, 2 from BNB women University, 3 from Arorr University of Arts and Heritage, and 2 from Ghulam Muhammad Mahar Medical University.

Description of Participants

- Participant must be teacher at higher education institute
- The posting must be at Sukkur District
- They must have 6 months experience of using ChatGPT
- They must have at least 6 months of teaching experience

Table 1

Demographics of sample

Name	Gender	Age (Years)	Designation	Teaching Experience (Years)	ChatGPT Experience (Months)
Faculty 1	Male	46	Assistant professor	7	6
Faculty 2	Female	44	Assistant professor	10	7
Faculty 3	Female	40	Lecturer	6	9
Faculty 4	Male	49	Assistant professor	10	18
Faculty 5	Female	38	Teaching Assistant	2	15
Faculty 6	Female	32	Teaching Assistant	1	6
Faculty 7	Male	52	Assistant professor	11	10
Faculty 8	Male	51	Assistant professor	10	14
Faculty 9	Female	44	Assistant Professor	6	08
Faculty 10	Male	48	Assistant Professor	8	12

The demographic information of participants shows that 5 male and 5 female participated in study showing the equal representation of both genders. While, the age breakdown is 32 and 52 showing that the faculty member from the mid-career and late career were part of study. The age breakdown shows that teachers of higher education level are taking interest in utilizing the ChatGPT in their teaching practices professional growth. The primary data in present study was gathered using the semi-structured interviews. According to the Creswell (2005) interview are the best form gathering the in-depth information on a particular event. Interviews were conducted by taking consent from the participants. Then, the data was analyzed by having utilized the thematic analysis. Before analyzing, the data was transcribed and the personal details of the participants were replaced with codes.

RESULTS & FINDINGS

Supports in Planning Instructions of Lessons

The data in present study revealed that the ChatGPT which is trending search engine is utilized by the faculty members of university for planning their instructions. As a respondent mentioned that F10, *“Teaching can be made effective by planning best instructions before delivering the lesson. So, ChatGPT has made it possible for the teachers to plan their instruction having its usage at fullest. I myself use ChatGPT whenever I plan my instruction.”* Based on the viewpoints of faculty members the ChatGPT offers wide range interacting activities that could be utilized for making classroom environment encouraging and interacting. ChatGPT provides an overview of the vast ideas and scenarios through which one can make changes in their instruction F2: *“planning the instruction is more hard than its implementation so whenever I think I am stuck, I just take out my mobile phone and starting searching on ChatGPT the required things. Believe me, it provides me with things which I haven’t even heard before. One of best features of ChatGPT I like the most is that it facilitates us with variety of ideas and activities which too easy to execute in our teaching”.*

According to the perceptions of faculty members ChatGPT is a problem-solving machine which solves the human problems with seconds whether they related to the teaching or personal lives of human. F4: *“I think ChatGPT is developed for the purpose of solving the problems of human. Because it has the solution of every problem even related to the personal lives of people. Though it does not solve the problem fully but at least gives us ideas through which we can tackle the situation in hand.”*

The analyzed data shows that faculty can use latest and best assessment strategies in their teaching for checking and diagnosing the understanding of students during the class or at the end of session. As a participant mentioned that F5: *“I become very angry when I think about the assessment of the students but after the invention of ChatGPT I do not feel any problem in assessing students progress because it provides me with various formative and summative assessment techniques which consider for assessing the students.”*

Influence Workflow of Educators

The findings of present study disclosed that ChatGPT influences the workflow of educators as they can now conclude their work of eight hours just in 2 hours because of the information provided by ChatGPT. It can be clearly understood that how efficient the ChatGPT is for the educators. One of the participants told that F 7: *“I use ChatGPT to for having brainstorming the new activities that could my save my time and I could incorporate into my teaching practices by keeping my students fresh and engaged.”* The analyzed showed that the ChatGPT is crucial for enhancing the workflow of teacher at higher education level. Without using ChatGPT educators might take time to for preparing their lectures and implementing while, they could do the same thing with less time by using ChatGPT. It was mentioned by a participant that F10: *“ChatGPT helps me a lot in planning my lecture that is full of interactive activities where students could be challenged to think critically.”*

Declines Students Skills

The findings showed that after the utilization of ChatGPT the students are declining their individual research skills. As observed by a faculty member F8: *“I have noticed that students who use ChatGPT in their research work are less likely to have manual skills of putting citations, references or other research related things.”* In addition, by adopting the ChatGPT students can have access of large amount of information thus, they have changed their learning styles. One of the participants observed that F5: *“by using Artificial intelligence students have access to huge amount of information so they have changed the way they learn and research.”* It was also found in the present study that there many students who use ChatGPT in their research work and they are too much addicted to this thing that they even do not make changes into their copied work. As mentioned by F2: *“students need to be made aware of the limitations of AI chatbots such as ChatGPT and for the necessity to critically evaluate the results they produce before blindly using them in their academic work.”*

Barriers and Boundaries of Using ChatGPT

Findings revealed that before integrating the technology into the teaching-learning process pupil must know the limitations of using it. As ChatGPT is a powerful tool of 21st technologies so before using it one should know the boundaries because the content generated by ChatGPT is already present on the internet which could lead to the plagiarism issues. A study by Lim et al. (2023) stated that *“faculty members in higher education institutions face academic integrity challenges with the use of ChatGPT. They must determine whether student submissions, such as assignments and research reports, are the result of the students’ original data analysis or whether they contain material plagiarized and recycled by ChatGPT”*. It was also highlighted by the participant F7: *“I have notice that ChatGPT generate wonderful and meaning ideas but copying those ideas exactly could plagiarize the whole work researchers”*. In a study it was mentioned by Montenegro-Rueda et al. (2023) that AI chatbots like ChatGPT can facilitate the students and teachers with individualized support and make their learning more efficient. But, they suggested to consider the barriers and boundaries related to these kind of technologies, such as privacy of individuals’ data etc.

Requires Continuous Professional Growth of Teachers

It was disclosed in the findings that adopting the technology old or trending version requires a great care. Hence, the educators need to undergo proper training programs. It was mentioned by one the participants that F2: *“technology is continuously upgrading hence, it requires the latest training. If I will attend the workshop or training sessions, I can use the ChatGPT or other technologies into my teaching in more better way. These training will enhance my skills related to the integration of ChatGPT.”* Further, it was also showed that collaboration could also lead the educators to have best teaching practices in their everyday teaching. As mentioned by a faculty member F9: *“In order learn and improve our technological skills we can also collaborate ou colleagues and other friend who are somehow expert in these skills. This will not only saves our cost but improves our bonding because the peer tutoring enhances the bond of friendship”*.

Discussion

The aim of present study was to explore how the ChatGPT impact teaching practices and professional growth of teachers at higher education institutions while, the findings are also similar to it. There were five major themes

in current study. The themes are; supports in planning instructions of lessons, influence workflow of educators, declines students skills, barriers and boundaries of using ChatGPT, and requires continuous professional growth of teachers. It was showed in the findings that ChatGPT is powerful tool in terms of facilitating students and teachers with huge amount of information specifically when teacher is preparing their lesson plans. It provides them various interactive which they can include to make their environment of the class lively. In this regard Ogurlu & Mossholder (2023) has mentioned that ChatGPT help the educators in their instruction planning providing them with various interactive activities they could have in their class. Additionally, it was also found that ChatGPT enhance the workflow of teachers because its features are user-friendly and easy to use. They can do the work of a week into few hours. On the contrary, Tan & Subramonyam (2023) in their study identified that the due to the invention of ChatGPT the work of educators has become too easy to do it on their fingertips.

Keeping view the research skills of students and teachers' it was found in the study that ChatGPT no doubt is useful for improving the quality of education but it declines the research skills of students. While, Berg & Plessis (2023) mentioned ChatGPT, the 21st century declines the skills like writing, critical and creativity skills of pupil because totally depend on it. Thus, their skills keep decline. Furthermore, it was also showed in the present study that integrating the ChatGPT in teaching practices make it more effective to teach but there is fear of having plagiarism into the content. According to the Montenegro-Rueda et al. (2023) technology could lead the users to the fear of plagiarism because it gives the information that can also be found on other sources of internet. However, the present study revealed that technology is such a tool which requires specific skill for its successful integration. The reason behind is that it keeps upgrading its versions. So, the individuals having knowledge about previous version of technology may not be able to use the latest version. Yu (2024) has also mentioned due to the changing of technology teachers need professional training for enhancing their technological skills.

CONCLUSION

The present study explored how the adoption of ChatGPT artificial intelligence AI impact on teaching practices and professional growth of teachers i.e. teaching assistants, lecturers, and professors. The study revealed ChatGPT is very useful for educators for making their teaching more interesting and interactive. It was disclosed in this study that ChatGPT is very helpful teachers in providing information related to the instruction they intending to deliver in the next session. It was also mentioned by the previous studies that the information provided by the AI chatbots can also be found on google search engines like google scholar and science direct. So, it was recommended in this study that while using the ChatGPT teachers should be aware about the copyright frauds. Additionally, study also showed that ChatGPT declines the research skills. It was also agreed by various studies of the past that people addicted to the ChatGPT become dependent and they, instead of focusing their critical skills, do copy paste to the information generated by ChatGPT. So, the study recommended that individuals who are utilizing the ChatGPT should first focus their skills and then take a little help from it which might not weaken their skills. However, the study suggested that the successful integration of ChatGPT requires skills related to its use. Hence, the teachers should be given appropriated training programs so that they might not face difficulty in utilizing the ChatGPT while delivering the lesson.

Competing Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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